

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in South Africa: An Introduction

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Local government is the provider of primary services, which are essential to the dignity of all who live in its area of jurisdiction. Ensuring the sustainable provision of services and encouraging the involvement of communities in the matters of local government are some of the main objects of local government.¹² In this regard, the Constitution calls for municipalities to strive within their financial and administrative capacity to achieve their constitutional mandate set out in Section 152. These objects are crucial in a country that seeks to rectify injustices of the previous apartheid local government- a local government system that deliberately excluded the majority of black citizens from accessing essential services. As such, both urban and rural local municipalities of the democratic local government are responsible mainly for essential services and infrastructure vital to communities' wellbeing.

The Constitution further sets out the framework for local government responsibilities. Section 156(1) of the Constitution provides that a municipality has executive authority, and the right to administer, the local government matters set out in Schedules 4B and 5B of the Constitution and any other matter assigned to a municipality by national or provincial legislation. Schedules 4B and 5B grant original powers to local government. Local government's functions must be observed in relation to the developmental mandate given to municipalities by the Constitution (Section 153).

Although at first glance the constitutional provision of local government powers and functions seems symmetrical, Section 156(1)(b),¹³ Section 155(3)(c)¹⁴ and the compulsory assignment per Section 156(4)¹⁵ of the Constitution show that there is a system of differentiation of powers and functions.

¹² Sec 152 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, states additional objects of local government as providing for a democratic and accountable government to local communities, promoting social and economic development, and promoting a safe and healthy environment.

¹³ Sec 156(1)(b) of the Constitution provides that '[a] municipality has executive authority in respect of, and has the right to administer any other matter assigned to it by national and provincial legislation'.

¹⁴ Sec 155(3)(c) of the Constitution provides that '[n]ational legislation must subject to Sec 229, make provision for an appropriate division of powers and functions between municipalities when an area has municipalities of both category B and category C. A division of powers and functions between a category B municipality and a category C municipality may differ from the division of powers and functions between another category B municipality and that category C municipality'.

¹⁵ Sec 156(4) of the Constitution states that '[t]he national and provincial governments must assign to a municipality, by agreement and subject to any conditions, the administration of a matter listed in Part A of

Division of Functions and Powers Between District and Local Municipalities

The relevant national legislation is the Municipal Structures Act 117 of 1998 and it must take into account the need to provide municipal services equitably and sustainably. The constitutional and legislative division of powers and provision of public services is not based on the urban-rural distinction. Legally, metropolitan, district and local municipalities have authority over urban areas. In practice, however, metropolitan and local municipalities govern in mostly urban areas while district municipalities generally govern in rural and semi-rural areas.

Section 83(3) of the Structures Act provides that a district municipality must seek to achieve the integrated, sustainable and equitable social and economic development of its area as a whole.¹⁶ This means that districts are to play a supportive role and must do so by providing the bulk services and district-wide functions set out in Section 84(1) of the Structures Act,¹⁷ and cater for both the district and local municipalities within the district's jurisdiction. Local municipalities have the powers provided in Sections 156 and 229 of the Constitution,¹⁸ excluding the district powers listed in Section 84(1) of the Structures Act.¹⁹ This division grants local municipalities most day-to-day service delivery functions. The division of powers has not been without problems due to poorly executed mandates as a result of capacity constraints, finances, as well as duplication of services, uneven development and poor relations between the district and local municipalities.

Further, the provision of municipal services must be done in a manner that ensures community participation and accountability. Therefore, integrated development planning (IDP) was introduced through the Municipal Systems Act of 2001 as a key strategic planning instrument for service delivery in local government. The emergence of IDP is strongly linked to the early 1990s drive towards addressing the legacy of apartheid through an integrated and participatory approach to planning.²⁰ Each municipality prepares an IDP in consultation and cooperation with the local community and other organs of state.²¹ This is in realisation of the fact that some municipal services must be delivered in a coordinated manner, for example,

Schedule 4 or Part A of Schedule 5 which necessarily relates to local government, if that matter would most effectively be administered locally and the municipality has the capacity to administer it'.

¹⁶ Act 117 of 1998.

¹⁷ The functions and powers of a district municipality include integrated development planning, portable water supply systems, bulk supply of electricity (transmission, distribution and where applicable, generation), domestic waste-water and sewage disposal systems, solid waste disposal sites, municipal roads, regulation of passenger transport services, municipal airports, municipal health services, firefighting services, fresh produce markets and abattoirs, cemeteries and crematoria, local tourism, municipal public works, grants given to the district (receipt, allocation and if applicable distribution) and taxes, levies and duties (imposition and collection).

¹⁸ These are Schedule 4B and 5B original powers, assigned powers and fiscal powers.

¹⁹ Sec 84(2) of the Structures Act.

²⁰ Anél du Plessis (ed), *Environmental Law and Local Government in South Africa* (Juta 2017) 168. For further discussion on the people's participation, see report section 6 on People's Participation in Local Decision-Making.

²¹ Sec 29 of the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000.

when planning for human settlement (housing), other related essential services such as roads, water, and electricity, waste removal, streetlights, public transport, and municipal health services must also be considered. Twenty-five years post-democracy, access to these municipal services has been expanded to previously marginalised communities. However, secondary data suggests an increasing trend of community protests in South Africa since the year 2010, with the highest manifesting in the Gauteng province, a province that is mainly comprised of urban local government (ULG) and deemed to be the economic hub. The reality is that of a local government battling to meet the communities' expectations as communities often exhibit signs of anger and dissatisfaction with the quality and quantity of services offered by the local government sphere. Based on the Constitution, the communities' expectations for municipal services are legitimate.

The Structures Act, on the other hand, provides a framework for authorisations and adjustments of functions between the district and local municipalities. The Minister of Local Government may authorise a local municipality to perform or exercise a power in respect of the water, electricity, sanitation and municipal health functions that ordinarily reside with district municipalities.²² Provincial MECs, on the other hand, are empowered to adjust the powers and functions from a local municipality to a district municipality or vice versa, except for integrated development planning, water, electricity, sanitation and municipal health functions, as well as grants made to district municipalities and collection of taxes or levies in respect of these functions.²³ The adjustment can only take place after a capacity assessment has been undertaken, and the Municipal Demarcation Board endorses the adjustment. Graph 1 shows the number of authorisations that have been made and that a large number of local municipalities are performing functions that are, according to Section 84(1) of the Structures Act, redistributive in nature and are district municipality functions.

Table 19: Ministerial Authorised functions performed by Local or District municipalities

Figure 1: Authorisations made by the Minister per Section 84(3) of the Structures Act.²⁴

²² Sec 84(3) of the Structures Act. The Minister must comply with the consultation requirements set out in this provision.

²³ Sec 85(1) of the Structures Act.

²⁴ Municipal Demarcation Board (MDB), 'Assessment of Municipal Powers and Function' (National Report, MDB 2018).

Additional Powers and Functions

The Constitution mandates the national and provincial government to assign the administration of a Schedule 4A or 5A matter to a municipality if the matter would be most effectively administered locally and the municipality has the capacity to administer the matter (Section 156(4) of the Constitution). A function can be assigned to a specific municipality or to all municipalities in general. An assignment is the secondary source of power for local government. The Constitution (Sections 99, 126 and 156(4)), and the Municipal Systems Act 32 of 2000,²⁵ set out the appropriate procedures for transferring functions to municipalities. The procedures are designed to warrant that the assignment of powers outside of the competencies set out in Schedule 4B and 5B are well placed, that municipalities are protected from unfunded mandates and that legislative and executive capacity is transferred to the assignee municipality.²⁶ Graphs 2 and 3 below show the Municipal Demarcation Board’s assessment of the number of municipalities performing functions that are originally national and provincial government functions. According to the graphs, a large number of these provincial and national functions are performed by local municipalities.

Figure 2: Performance of Schedule 4A and 5A functions by municipalities

Figure 2: MDB’s assessment of the number of district and local municipalities that currently perform functions that are not local government’s original functions.²⁷

²⁵ Secs 10 and 10A of the Municipal Systems Act.

²⁶ Jaap de Visser and Annette Christmas, ‘Reviewing Local Government Functions’ (2007) 9 Local Government Bulletin 13.

²⁷ MDB, ‘Assessment of Municipal Powers and Function’, above.

Figure 24: Municipalities administering Schedule 4A or 5A functions

Figure 3: District and local municipalities that currently administer functions that are not local government’s original functions.²⁸

Adjustments to Adapt to Changes

Metropolitan municipalities exercise all the original powers of local government enumerated in the Constitution. At present, they cannot adapt their provision of public services to demographic changes in their jurisdiction because there is no framework governing adjustments in metropolitan municipalities. The process of assignment provided in the Constitution could, however, be used to empower municipalities to adapt to changes. For example, municipalities want to perform more housing, public transport and health responsibilities. All these functions fall under Schedules 4A and 5A of the Constitution, making them national and provincial government functions but they could be assigned to municipalities.

Alternative Service Delivery Mechanisms

Municipalities in South Africa have the discretion to use alternative service delivery mechanisms to provide various municipal services that were previously performed internally. The section below outlines two such mechanisms that may be employed.

Use of Municipal Entities as Service Providers

Municipal entities can be established for this purpose.²⁹ A municipal entity is an ‘organ of state’ and must comply with the legislative framework that applies to its parent municipality to

²⁸ *ibid.*

²⁹ Centre for Applied Legal Studies (CALs), ‘Evaluating the Efficiency and Effectiveness of Municipal Entities as Municipal Service Delivery Mechanisms – A Legal Assessment’ (CALs 2010) 23. The following types of municipal

ensure accountability, transparency and consultative processes. Municipal entities are accountable to the municipality or municipalities that established them. The municipal entity enters into a service delivery agreement with its parent municipality and must perform its duties according to the objectives set by the parent municipality. Municipal entities, unlike municipalities, function on business principles and are expected to be free from municipal problems such as inefficiency, slowness and unresponsiveness.³⁰

Municipal entities are mainly used by metropolitan municipalities, some district municipalities and some local municipalities that have the capacity. The 2017-18 Auditor General's Audit Report for Local Government shows that in the 2017-18 financial year, 57 municipal entities were operating across both urban and rural municipalities.³¹ This could be due to the scope and variety of services they have to provide, as well as the demographical make-up of the area(s) they have to provide the services in. Key issues to be considered in comparing the performance of entities with that of internal service delivery by the municipality include management capacity, the specific context of the municipality, political and community accountability, and performance monitoring and reporting. While municipal entities cannot be seen as a solution for service delivery, in certain contexts they may be more effective than internal delivery. For example, in the City of Johannesburg Metropolitan Municipality, the water and sanitation services are provided by the municipal entity Johannesburg Water.³² In uThungulu District Municipality, the fresh produce market function is performed by the UThungulu Fresh Produce Market.³³

Contracting with Private Parties

Section 217 of the Constitution states the constitutional framework for procurement by an organ of state in the national, provincial or local sphere of government.³⁴ When procuring goods and services at a municipal level, Chapter 11 of the Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) comes into operation and it must be read together with the Preferential Public Policy Framework Act, as well as Chapter 8 of the Municipal Systems Act. Section 111 of the MFMA mandates every municipality and municipal entity to have and implement Supply Chain Management (SCM).³⁵ The SCM Regulations issued in terms of the MFMA lay down the

entities are recognised in the Systems Act – private company (subject to restrictions), a service utility (established by a municipality) and a multi-jurisdictional service utility (established by two or more municipalities).

³⁰ Felicity Kitchin, 'Consolidation of Research Conducted on Municipal Entities in South Africa' (2010) 4-5.

³¹ Kimi Makwetu, 'Local Government Audit Report 2017/18' (Auditor General 2019) Annexure 1.

³² City of Johannesburg, 'City of Johannesburg Annual Report 2017/18' 60-71.

³³ uThungulu District Municipality, 'uThungulu District Municipality Annual Report 2017/18'.

³⁴ Sec 217(1) of the Constitution requires the contracting of goods or services to take place in accordance with a system that is fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost-effective. Sec 217(3) of the Constitution requires that national legislation prescribe a framework within which the preferential procurement policy referred to in Sec 217(2) must be implemented. The Preferential Public Policy Framework Act (PPPFA) was promulgated as a response to this constitutional imperative.

³⁵ Sec 112 of the MFMA.

requirements for the governance of procurement processes. Municipalities have to determine their own procedures and policies, which must be consistent with the legislative framework. If the contract imposes financial obligations on the municipality beyond three years, Section 33 of the MFMA comes into operation and mandates the municipality to consult the local community,³⁶ National Treasury and the responsible national department if the contract involves the provision of water, sanitation and electricity. Both urban and rural municipalities have to follow this legislative framework when awarding business to private companies.

Municipalities also have the discretion to enter into Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) for the provision of services³⁷ and infrastructure. This discretion is, however, heavily regulated by the National Treasury and in terms of the Municipal Systems Act.³⁸ At local government level, PPPs are regulated under the MFMA and its regulations,³⁹ which provides a framework for municipalities and private sector partners to enter into mutually beneficial commercial transactions, for the public good. PPPs are often used for procuring capital projects and as such the process followed is intensive and requires competitive and transparent bidding, as well as the capacity for the municipality to carry out the projects. While legislation and policy do not differentiate between PPPs for urban or rural areas/government, the procedural requirements of a PPP suggest that a municipality must have the capacity to undertake the strenuous procedure before engaging in the actual substance of the partnership.⁴⁰ A PPP has to be strongly motivated, especially with regards to the long term nature of the contract, as well as a municipality's financial viability before, during and after the PPP has been completed.

One of the PPPs that have improved the lives of the citizens in the City of Tshwane was a partnership between the municipality and the South African Breweries (SAB) in 2018, where SAB rehabilitated two water pump stations – Groenkloof springs and Kentron borehole to increase the municipality's water supply. The partnership resulted in an additional 7.5 million litres of water for residents per day.⁴¹

³⁶ See report section 6 on People's Participation in Local Decision-Making.

³⁷ If the PPP involves the provision of a municipal service, chapter 8 of the Systems Act must also be complied with.

³⁸ See Secs 76-78 and 80-81 of the Municipal Systems Act.

³⁹ Sec 120 of the MFMA. Read together with the Municipal PPP Regulations (2005), the Local Government SCM Regulations (2005) and National Treasury's Municipal Services and PPP Guidelines.

⁴⁰ See Sec 120(2), (4) and (6) of the MFMA.

⁴¹ '2025 Sustainability Goals' (*Greenovation*, 16 May 2018) <

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